

New records of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Sterea Ellas, Greece

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ABSTRACT. New records of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Sterea Ellas, Greece.

27 ant species are recorded from the western part of Sterea Ellas region (Western Greece), 13 of them are new to this region. The current list of ants of Sterea Ellas comprises 90 species.

KEY WORDS: ants, Greece-Sterea Ellas, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

Ant fauna of Greece is probably the richest in Europe, with about 280 recorded species and about 20 of them endemic to this country. However, the individual geographic regions are very unevenly studied (LEGAKIS 2011, BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012, 2013, BOROWIEC 2014). Macedonia has richest ant fauna, with at least 158 species recorded, followed by Thrace (116), Dodecanese (111), Ionian Islands (107), Aegean Islands (106), Peloponnese (102), Crete (98), Epirus (87), Sterea Ellas (77), Thessaly (67), Cyclades (46) respectively (LEGAKIS 2011 and BOROWIEC & SALATA unpublished data). Sterea Ellas, covering an area of 24,818.3 km², with 77 recorded species, is one of the poorest known regions. Although this region is a centre of scientific studies on ants in the Zoological Museum, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens the western part of the region is poorly studied because most records and most collections of ants from Sterea Ellas originated from its eastern part.

At the turn of August and September 2016 on the sidelines of research on ants of Epirus region we had a chance to investigate 6 sites located in the western Sterea Ellas. As a result we collected 27 species of ants, including 13 new to the region.

LIST OF SPECIES

We give the list of collected species in particular collecting sites. Species new to Sterea Ellas are marked with an asterisk. Locality numbers refer to the position in the coding system used in the Database and Collection of Greek Ants preserved at the University of Wrocław.

STE-378 – 2.4 km SW Monastiraki, 38,83055 / 20,93071, 420 m, 31 VIII 2016, oak forest:

Aphaenogaster balcanica (EMERY), **Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ), *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR), *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR),

Messor wasmanni KRAUSSE, *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*, *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE), **Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAIEV); *Temnothorax exilis* (EMERY), **Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, and *Tetramorium* cf. *semilaeve*.

STE-379 – 4.2 km S Monastiraki, 38,81241 / 20,93778, 610 m, 31 VIII 2016, oak forest:

Aphaenogaster balcanica (EMERY), *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER), **Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR), **Lasius lasioides* (EMERY), *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR), *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER), *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*, *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE), **Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL), and **Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY.

STE-380 – 2.8 km N Vatos, 38,78302 / 20,98382, 1090 m, 31 VIII 2016, mountain pastures with oak shrubs:

Aphaenogaster balcanica (EMERY), *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER), *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER), **Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL, *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR), *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR), *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, *Myrmoxenus gordiagini* RUZSKY –2w; *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*, *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE), **Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAIEV), **Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, **Temnothorax* cf. *unifasciatus*, and *Tetramorium* cf. *semilaeve*.

STE-381 – 1.8 km SW of Thirio, 38,84088 / 20,97326, 760 m, 31 VIII 2016, oak shrubs:

Camponotus dalmaticus (NYLANDER), *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER), **Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR), *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE), *Temnothorax exilis* (EMERY), and **Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT).

STE-395 – Psila Alonia, 38,96255 / 21,19527, 62 m, 4 IX 2016, stream valley with plane-tree forest:

Aphaenogaster balcanica (EMERY), **Aphaenogaster* cf. *muelleriana*, *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea*, *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER), *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER), *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ), *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR), **Dolichoderes quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS), **Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*, *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE), **Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica*, **Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAIEV), and *Temnothorax* cf. *turcicus*.

STE-396 – 1.6 km N Xirolivado, 38,98628 / 21,21172, 300 m, 4 IX 2016, stream valley with plane-tree forest:

Aphaenogaster balcanica (EMERY), *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea*, *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER), *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER), *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ), *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR), **Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, and *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*.

DISCUSSION

Among the collected material, the most interesting species are: *Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL, a species endemic to Greece, hitherto known only from Kephallonia island, *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, recorded only from Ionian Islands and Peloponnese, and *Aphaenogaster* cf. *muelleriana*, probably a new species or subspecies of

Aphaenogaster ovaticeps complex, so far collected only in Sterea Ellas and Peloponnese. Our sample of an arboricolous species *Temnothorax* cf. *turcicus* is different from *T. turcicus* that occurs in Central Europe and eastern Greece and is probably new to science. We collected this morphospecies only in lowland oak forest and platane-tree forests from Epirus to southern Peloponnese. Our data raised the number of known species from the Sterea Ellas region to 90.

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REFERENCES

- BOROWIEC L. 2014. Catalogue of ants of Europe, the Mediterranean Basin and adjacent regions (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus (Special issue – Monograph)* 25: 1–340.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2012. Ants of Greece – checklist, comments and new faunistic data (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* 23: 461–563.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2013. Ants of Greece – additions and corrections (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* 24: 335–401.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2014. Redescription of *Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL, 1889, new status and notes on ants from Kefalonia, Greece (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* 25: 499–517.
- LEGAKIS A. 2011. Annotated list of the ants (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) of Greece. *Hellenic Zoological Archives* 7: 1–55.

STRESZCZENIE

Nowe stanowiska mrówek (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) z regionu Sterea Ellas w Grecji

Podano nowe stanowiska dla 27 gatunków mrówek zbieranych w zachodniej części geograficznego regionu Sterea Ellas (Prowincja Grecja Zachodnia), 13 gatunków stwierdzono w tym regionie po raz pierwszy. Aktualna lista gatunków mrówek znanych z regionu Sterea Ellas wzrosła do 90.

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